

Impact of gender of the employee on anxiety, depression and stress

Dr. Seeta¹; Raj Kumar²

¹Assistant professor, Dept of Psychology, Uttarakhand Open University, Haldwani, Uttarakhand, India

²Post Graduate Scholar, Dept of Psychology, Uttarakhand Open University, Haldwani, Uttarakhand, India

Corresponding Author Email: seetakohli74@gmail.com

Abstract— Anxiety have become common problem for human. The purpose of this study was to investigate impact of gender on employee's level of anxiety depression and stress at the Industrial level. The descriptive survey research method was used for the study and the sample consisted of 40 employee (20 male and 20 female) which were selected randomly from Industrial Siddcul area, Haridwar, Uttarakhand. The scale was used for data collection Anxiety, depression and stress scale (ADSS) by Bhatnagar, Singh and Pandey (2011) was used to assess anxiety, depression and stress. Where gender was considered as independent variables and anxiety, depression and stress as dependent variables. data were analysis by Mean, SD and 't' values. The result of the study showed that: (1) There is significant difference between male and female employee in their anxiety level. (2) There is significant difference between male and female employee in their depression level. (3) There is significant difference between male and female employee in their stress level. Based on research findings, researchers suggest that the psychological counselling services of Industrial employee must be functionalized and improved to moderate employee's anxiety, depression and stress level.

Keywords- Anxiety, Depression, Stress

I. INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is a state experienced in anticipation of danger or threat, even when such danger or threat is not currently present or cannot be specified. Anxiety disorder is a mental health condition characterized by excessive and irrational fear and worry. It manifests as feelings of tension, worried thoughts, and physiological changes like increased blood pressure. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 280 million people suffered from anxiety in 2019, including 23 million children and adolescents. Research conducted by Barlow in 2002 describes anxiety as an uncontrolled, diffuse, unpleasant, and persistent state of negative affect, accompanied by physical symptoms of stress and heightened alertness.

Depression, on the other hand, is a constant feeling of sadness and loss of interest that interferes with normal activities. In 2019, 280 million people were living with depression, including 23 million children and adolescents. The DSM-5 defines depression as a mood disorder characterized by persistent feelings of sadness and loss of interest.

According to Thomas G. Plante (2006), depression is a heterogeneous illness with various subtypes. Its explanatory mechanisms are critical to understand, and multiple factors contribute to its incidence. Psychosocial therapies and antidepressant medications are commonly used for treating depression. Chronic depression may require a combination of both approaches. The impact of depression can be both short-term and long-term, affecting work and social life depending on the specific type of depression.

Stress: Nowadays, the definition of stress is the process of interaction resulting from environmental demands. According to the renowned psychologists Lazarus and Folkman (1984), stress occurs when individuals perceive that the demands from external situations exceed their coping capacity. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines stress as a state of worry or mental tension caused by challenging situations. It is a natural human response that compels us to address challenges and threats in our lives.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mental disorders are widespread globally, and the prevalence of affected individuals continues to rise (Twenge et al., 2019). Anxiety, depression, and stress constitute "major disturbances in an individual's thinking, feelings, or behavior," leading to challenges in social, work, or family activities (APA, 2015). Schaefer and colleagues (2017) highlight that the number of individuals who remain free from mental stress, depression, and anxiety throughout their lifetime is remarkably small. Furthermore, organizations should be

alarmed by these statistics, as clinical manifestations of mental disorders—such as anxiety, depression, and stress—are among the most common causes of long-term sickness absence (Mittendorfer-Rutz et al., 2012; Suzuki et al., 2015).

In their study, Steel et al. (2014) examine how clinical diagnoses of three prevalent mental disorders—depression, anxiety, and stress-related disorders—spread across different organizations through employee mobility and social transmission. Management researchers have primarily focused on the latter aspect, arguing that work-related stressors, including aversive working conditions characterized by high job demands, increase the risk of employees developing mental disorders (Joyce et al., 2016; Follmer and Jones, 2017; Harvey et al., 2017).

Thi and colleagues (Thi et al., 2021) emphasize that organizational employees rely on various factors, such as company objectives, management style, employee belief systems, and operational environments. Although these employees have varying effects on motivation levels and performance, they tend to work harder toward achieving company goals when they perceive themselves as integral parts of the organizational environment. Fakhri and associates (Fakhri et al., 2020) argue that a clan culture—where all employees have equal power and the staff fosters a family-like mentality—allows team members to feel supported and valued. These positive feelings enhance employee engagement and well-being.

Saha and Kumar (Saha et al. 2018) support these findings by describing company beliefs as the moderator of job satisfaction and affective commitment among employees. Highly-satisfied employees tend to be more committed to the success of their organizations.

A researcher Rahawarin analyses and understand the concept of reward for employees who demonstrate organizational values. Happy employees are more productive and highly engaged in the workplace (Rahawarin et al. 2021). Organizations with more equal gender opportunity, engaged workers tend to have more revenues compared to those with less-involved ones. Modern-day organizations endeavor to realize profitability, fast growth, continued improvement, and future preparation. Organizations need to identify the factors impacting performance to achieve high productivity. In their study on the linkage between corporate equal opportunity to gender and job enjoyment, Maswani and Rina (Maswani et al. 2019) established that a strong equal opportunity to workers is a key to good performance. Positive and robust corporate beliefs can encourage brilliant individual performance. Conversely, weak and negative beliefs may cause demotivation and dissuade outstanding employees from meeting their potential [Dong et al. 2020]. Employees work hard in environments with good mental health, (Stojanovi, et al. 2020) that have a clear sense of direction and purpose. Well-coordinated, integrated, and highly consistent environments are a powerful stability source for employees. Employee performance in such environments often occurs in the form of greater productivity, higher customer satisfaction levels, reduced turnover, lower absenteeism levels, and higher customer satisfaction rates. The level of adaptability competence can support positive outcomes related to increased work capability and career success. This competency can also facilitate organizational results, such as learning, change management, and sustaining shifting customer expectations (Park, et al. 2019). Due to the pressure of working hard to meet external objectives, this culture may make it challenging for employees to engage with their work meaningfully (Bhui et al. 2016). Pressure may, in turn, translate to workplace stress and have adverse repercussions on the mental welfare of workers. Workplace stress increases the risk of burnout, depression, anxiety, and substance abuse disorders among employees. A scientific study by Gao (Gao, Y. 2015) found that clan cultures and free from anxiety, depression, stress contain unique attributes, such as interpersonal cohesiveness, loyalty, and tradition, which results in a lack of attention in managing market needs and adversely influences market orientation.

Stress, anxiety and depression are a physical and mental condition that affects a person's effectiveness, productivity, health, and quality of work. Indeed, perceived worker's stress makes workers to decrease their job satisfaction seriously and reduced quality of worker's performance. Workplace stress anxiety, depression emerges from different factors, such as workplace conflict, family issues, role ambiguity, work overload, and a hostile working environment (Mrali et al. 2017). Whatever the cause of stress is within the workplace, high-stress levels influence the employees' engagement levels, burnout, and performance. Hence, organizations need to have well-defined interventions to reduce the impact of workplace stressors on the employee's well-being and productivity. According to Patro and Kumar (Patro et al. 2019) engagement in all these stress management strategies & psychological counselling positively influences the employee's productivity levels, reduces labor turnover, improves interpersonal relations, reduces absenteeism, and promotes physical and mental health.

Thus, organizations with influential clan culture promote employee adaptability competency and might reduce the prevalence of work-related stress, anxiety, and depression among adaptable employees. Based on the findings of the past studies, the current

researchers reasonably anticipate that clan culture, healthy environment, guidance and counselling from experience psychologist is more reliable strategy to augment the employee's adaptability competency and reduce their chances of experiencing work place from anxiety, depression and stress. Various studies have reported that stress is the prime determinant influencing employee performance. (Darvishmotevali M., Ali F,2020)

III. OBJECTIVES

To examine the Anxiety among Male and Female employee.

To examine the Depression among Male and Female employee.

To examine the Stress among Male and Female employee.

III.I. HYPOTHESES

The purpose of the present research was to investigate the following research hypotheses-

- There is no significant difference between Male and Female employee with dimension on anxiety.
- There is no significant difference between Male and Female employee with dimension on depression.
- There is no significant difference between Male and Female employee with dimension on stress.

IV. METHODS

IV.I. POPULATION AND SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

Descriptive survey method was used by the investigator to collect the relevant information for the research. In the present study the sample consisted of 40 employees (20 male and 20 females selected through random sampling technique from Industrial Siddcul area, Haridwar, Uttarakhand.

IV.II. TOOLS USED IN THE STUDY

For the data collection, investigator used the Anxiety, depression and stress scale (ADSS) by Bhatnagar, Singh and Pandey (2011) This test consists of 48 statements with 'yes' and 'no'

statements are awarded 0, 1 marks respectively. The researcher created a personal information form to collect information of the subjects, which contained the subject's sex, age, religion, work status, economic status, educational level, family status etc.

IV.III. DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study has been done only on the *employees of Siddcul area Haridwar* district.

- The study included young people who were between 25 and 45 years old.
- The study included only people of Hindu religion and not of other religions.
- The study included only *employees of Industrial Siddcul area, Haridwar,*

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data was analyzed by used statistical techniques like, Mean, SD and t-test.

Table-1

Anxiety score of Male and female

Group	Total score	N	Mean	SD	SEM	DF	t-value
Male	39	20	1.95	1.50	0.34	38	3.6814
Female	87	20	4.35	2.50	0.58		

It is clear from the above table that 20 male *employees of Siddcul area* have a mean anxiety of 1.95 and the standard deviation is 1.50. The mean scale of anxiety for a total of 20 Female *employees* is 4.35. The standard deviation is 2.50. The value of 't' obtained is 3.6814 which is more than the value of t at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance.

That is, there is significant difference between the anxiety of male and Female *employees*. The findings of the not supported first hypothesis

Table-2

Depression score of Male and female

Group	Total score	N	Mean	SD	SEM	DF	t-value
Male	25	20	1.25	1.21	0.27	38	2.7964
Female	67	20	3.35	3.13	0.70		

It is clear from the above table that 20 male *employees of Siddcul area* have a mean Depression of 1.25 and the standard deviation is 1.21. The mean scale of Depression for a total of 20 Female *employees* is 3.35. The standard deviation is 3.13. The value of 't' obtained is 2.7964 which is more than the value of t at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance.

That is, there is significant difference between the Depression of male and Female *employees*. The findings of the not supported second hypothesis.

Table-3

Stress score of Male and female

Group	Total score	N	Mean	SD	SEM	DF	t-value
Male	47	20	2.35	2.16	0.48	38	4.4824
Female	123	20	6.15	3.12	0.70		

It is clear from the above table that 20 male *employees of Siddcul area* have a mean Stress of 2.35 and the standard deviation is 2.16. The mean scale of Stress for a total of 20 Female *employees* is 6.15. The standard deviation is 3.12. The value of 't' obtained is 4.4824 which is more than the value of t at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. That is, there is significant difference between the Stress of male and Female *employees*. The findings of the not supported third hypothesis,

Conclusions: (1) There is significant difference between male and female employee in their anxiety level. (2) There is significant difference between male and female employee in their depression level. (3) There is significant difference between male and female employee in their stress level. a global study conducted by Kessler et al. (2015) showed that 45.7% of people who suffered from a depressive disorder in their lifetime had also suffered from one or more anxiety disorders. Sex differences for anxiety and depression are also observed starting from puberty onwards, with a higher vulnerability among females than males (Altemus et al., 2014; Baxter et al., 2014; Remes et al., 2016; Lim et al., 2018).

Based on our research findings, we recommend that psychological counseling services for industrial employees be enhanced to mitigate anxiety, depression, and stress levels. Employers should emphasize employee health wellness and stress-management, while

making employee participation official. suggest that the psychological counselling services of Industrial employee must be functionalized and improved to moderate employee's anxiety, depression and stress level

REFERENCES

1. AbuAlRub, R. F. (2004). Job stress, job performance, and social support among hospital nurses. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 36, 73–78.
2. Altemus, M., Sarvaiya, N., & Neill Epperson, C. (2014). Sex differences in anxiety and depression: Clinical perspectives. *Frontiers in Neuroendocrinology*, 35, 320–330. DOI: 10.1016/j.yfrne.2014.05.004
3. Darvishmotevali, M., & Ali, F. (2020). Job insecurity, subjective well-being, and job performance: The moderating role of psychological capital. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 87, 102462. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102462
4. Fakhri, M., Syarifuddin, S., Winarno, A., Nurnida, I., & Hanum, S. (2020). Democratic leadership practice to construct clan organizational culture in family companies. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 8, 803–811.
5. Follmer, K. B., & Jones, K. S. (2017). Mental illness in the workplace: An interdisciplinary review and organizational research agenda. *Journal of Management*, 44, 325–351.
6. Hussain, S. D., Khaliq, A., Nisar, Q. A., Kamboh, A. Z., & Ali, S. (2019). The impact of employees' recognition, rewards, and job stress on job performance: Mediating role of perceived organization support. *SEISENSE Journal of Management*, 2, 69–82.
7. Jamal, M. (2011). Job stress, job performance, and organizational commitment in a multinational company: An empirical study in two countries. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2, 20–29.
8. Joyce, S., Modini, M., Christensen, H., Mykletun, A., Bryant, R., Mitchell, P. B., & Harvey, S. B. (2016). Workplace interventions for common mental disorders: A systematic meta-review. *Psychological Medicine*, 46, 683–697.
9. Karasek, R. A. (1979). Job demands, job decision latitude, and mental strain: Implications for job redesign. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24, 285–308.
10. Kessler, R. C., Sampson, N. A., Berglund, P., Gruber, M. J., Al-Hamzawi, A., Andrade, L., et al. (2015). Anxious and non-anxious major depressive disorder in the World Health Organization World Mental Health Surveys. *Epidemiology and Psychiatric Sciences*, 24, 210–226. DOI: 10.1017/S2045796015000189
11. Khuong, M. N., & Yen, V. H. (2016). Investigate the effects of job stress on employee job performance: A case study at Dong Xuyen industrial zone, Vietnam. *International Journal of Trade, Economics, and Finance*, 7, 31.
12. Masoud, M., & Tariq, M. U. (2020). Improving employee induction and workplace culture development progress using lean six sigma methodology. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7, 5025–5036.
13. Maswani, S. T. Y. R., & Rina, A. (2019). The relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction towards organizational commitment and employee performance. *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 4, 144–152.
14. Mittendorfer-Rutz, E., Kjeldgård, L., Runeson, B., Perski, A., Melchior, M., Head, J., & Alexanderson, K. (2012). Sickness absence due to specific mental diagnoses and all-cause and cause-specific mortality: A cohort study of 4.9 million inhabitants of Sweden. *PloS One*, 7(9), e45788.
15. Nikpour, A. (2017). The impact of organizational culture on organizational performance: The mediating role of employee's organizational commitment. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 6, 65.
16. Park, S., & Park, S. (2019). Employee adaptive performance and its antecedents: Review and synthesis. *Human Resource Development Review*, 18, 294–324.
17. Remes, O., Brayne, C., Linde, R., & van der Lafortune, L. (2016). A systematic review of reviews on the prevalence of anxiety disorders in adult populations. *Brain and Behavior*, 6, e00497. DOI: 10.1002/brb3.497

- 18.Saha, S., & Kumar, S. P. (2018). Organizational culture as a moderator between affective commitment and job satisfaction. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 31, 184–206.
- 19.Schaefer, J. D., Caspi, A., Belsky, D. W., Harrington, H., Houts, R., Horwood, L. J., Horwood, L. H., et al. (2017). Enduring mental health: Prevalence and prediction. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 126, 212–224.
- 20.Singh, V., & Singh, M. (Year not specified). A burnout model of job crafting: Multiple mediator effects on job performance.
- 21.Steel, Z., Marnane, C., Iranpour, C., Chey, T., Jackson, J. W., Patel, V., & Silove, D. (2014). The global prevalence of common mental disorders: A systematic review and meta-analysis 1980–2013. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 43, 476–493.
- 22.Thi, T. D. P., Ngo, A. T., Duong, N. T., & Pham, V. K. (2021). The influence of organizational culture on employees' satisfaction and commitment in SMEs: A case study in Vietnam. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 8, 1031–1038.
- 23.Twenge, J. M., Cooper, A. B., Joiner, T. E., Duffy, M. E., & Binau, S. G. (2019). Age, period, and cohort trends in mood disorder indicators and suicide-related outcomes in a nationally representative dataset, 2005–2017. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 128, 185–199.
- 24.Vijayan, M. (2017). Impact of job stress on employees' job performance in Aavin, Coimbatore. *Journal of Organizational and Human Behavior*, 6, 21–29.
- 25.Wang, W., & Seifert, R. (2021). Job stress and employee outcomes: Employment practices in a charity. *Employment Relations*, 43, 1178–1193.
- 26.Yozgat, U., Yurtkoru, S., & Bilginoglu, E. (2013). Job stress and job performance among employees in the public sector in Istanbul: Examining the moderating role of emotional intelligence. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 75, 518–524.
- 27.Zacharias, T., Rahawarin, M. A., & Yusriadi, Y. (2021). Cultural reconstruction and organization environment for employee performance. *Journal of Ethnographic and Cultural Studies*, 8, 296–315.